
ANTI-CORRUPTION AND COMPLIANCE MONITORING: LEGAL LITERACY AMONG LAWYERS AND LAW STUDENTS

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Abstract: The world has become quite dynamic and new technologies have seen an unprecedented increase that created limitless opportunities, ranging from acquiring basic knowledge to employing the state-of-the-art devices for human-beings in the fashion world. This article illustrates key factors in the frame of legal literacy via paying attention to legal awareness, the concept and objects of legal literacy as well as the methods to develop legal literacy among lawyers and students who are in the law sphere all over the world. This article also emphasizes the importance of legal literacy during the lifespan of every individual who faces some issues which are associated with legal actions. By making an in depth research in the area of legal literacy among lawyers and students, the given article gives a wealth of information that formulates an overall understanding of the topic.

Keywords: law sphere, legal literacy, new technologies, legal awareness, concept, methods, key factors, lawyers.

I. Introduction

Legal literacy has played a crucial role among not only lawyers but also whole society too in the fast-growing world. Legal awareness, sometimes called public legal education or legal literacy, is the empowerment of individuals regarding issues involving the law.^[1] Legal awareness helps to promote consciousness of legal culture, participation in the formation of laws and the rule of law^{[2][3]}. Distinct from the education of students in law school seeking a degree in law (which is often simply called "legal education") and the continuing professional education of lawyers and judges (which is sometimes called "continuing legal education"), public legal education is principally aimed at people who are not lawyers, judges, or degree-seeking law students. With the help of legal literacy People must be made aware of the procedures and policies available for their betterment: raise awareness among populations. This article aims to explore the significant points of the topic that is not familiar to people at all.

A basic knowledge of law has become necessary for all those who are engaged in administration, trade or industry. Hence, a change in the quality, content and complexion of legal education is now viewed as a great social necessity. Thus there is

a need to bring awareness with people for their rights and duties, as well as remedies^[4]. Furthermore this article will emphasize a significant influence of legal literacy in every field in the interdependent world.

II. Methodology

This article carries out research on the theme of legal literacy and compile the most pressing information with the help of law, various databases, academic journals and legal documents in wide range of fields including law sphere, administration, trade or industry. Additionally, this article consists of practical approaches which carried out to consolidate legal awareness among developed nations.

III. Results

The article aims to reveal the imperfections, shortcomings and positive sides of legal literacy. Moreover it urges people to acquire basic aspects of this legal literacy in order to prevent legal issues that would be a real concern in the fields ranging from applying for a job, preparing legal documents to domestic court, being aware of our rights and so forth.

IV. Discussion

The last two decades have seen a whopping increase in Legal literacy that revolutionized the way people conduct legal actions adequately in their daily lives when they confront them. To become literate (able to read and write) is to become a full member of a written language community. If someone is only capable of oral expression, they are not a full member of the community that uses the written word. Being able to write extends the range of a person’s words far beyond hearing distance; being able to read vastly increases the number of other people whose words can be experienced. Being literate is considered such an important capacity that the United Nations has labelled it a human right. That is because Legal literacy invariably has been described as essential to the society widely^[5].

Originally, the term legal literacy was used to refer to an aspect of professional legal education. To be legally literate meant that you, as a lawyer, were capable of reading and writing the legal arguments, briefs, opinions, judgments, and legislation that contribute to the body of law. This definition describes legal literacy as being “literate in the law.” In this sense, legal literacy is primarily a concern of legal writing programs in law schools that teach students to think and communicate “like lawyers.” Later, a broader meaning of legal literacy became more common as a result of two different approaches to the concept. One approach considers legal literacy as a capacity spread along a continuum, with lawyers and judges at one end and relatively incapable non-lawyers (“laypersons”) at the other. This approach was adopted by the legal scholar James Boyd White, who considered legal literacy

to mean “that degree of competence in legal discourse required for meaningful and active life in our increasingly legalistic and litigious culture.”³ Another legal writer describes legal literacy as a “spectrum of functional skills”⁴ related to the conduct of litigation. According to the continuum approach, a certain degree of legal literacy is required for effective participation in modern society, but it is not necessary for the average citizen to reach the professional standard that law schools traditionally require^[6]. Modern life can be demanding for individuals, as they can require literacy in many areas beyond reading and writing. Legal literacy has been argued as an access to justice issue and required to ensure a healthy democracy. Also, being able to engage with the economy through a business can be an important avenue to access economic opportunities. However, the world of commerce is underpinned by legal requirements, and an understanding of these requirements may assist with compliance behavior, it is important that the legal literacy of these non-lawyer intermediaries is adequate.^[7] Legal literacy is that where one needs to have some broad information about legal provisions and processes.^[8]

Methods adopted to promote legal awareness among populations worldwide. **Legal literacy creates a perception of the legal culture and overall framework of establishment and formulation of the law at large.**^[9] There have been many cases where governments have promoted long-term legal literacy missions or awareness campaigns. Legal awareness enables people to demand justice, reliability and remedies at every level of their existence.^[10] An example of this is when institutions arrange legal literacy events. Legal awareness is also achieved through camps, lectures, and interactive workshops or crash programs on the essential and elementary legal laws. Among the general public, many wish to spend time listening to scholars on contemporary issues that have significant bearing on the rights and livelihood of ordinary people. Other methods are road shows, radio talks, street and theatre plays, as well as the publication of relevant books, periodicals, posters, and charts that deal with particular laws, the distribution of pamphlets, brochures, and stickers, the display of paintings, illustrations in comics, and other ways to ensure publicity for various legal mobilisation activities. Strategically located display boards in public places (railway stations, bus stations, market places, in front of major government offices and police stations) are also used to help government officials, police, and the public to understand the spirit of law.

Conclusion

This article explored the topic of legal literacy and gave an explanation of it among lawyers and law students and people as well. It is apparent that raising awareness of law literacy play a significant role in any society in the digital age in every field that is linked to legal documentation. By raising up young population with

legal knowledge via conducting approaches in areas including education, publications and advertisement. As a consequence of these practical approaches, it would be possible to prevent illiteracy which results in serious problems in the society . In the computer era lawyers and law students cannot visualize their legal actions without law literacy that makes them be aware of law sphere. To sum up, legal literacy has become inseparable part of our lives in recent years.

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